

About Improving Training Efficiency of Artistic Gymnasts in Preparation for Competition

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Abstract:

Sports competitions, as a unique activity, play a major role in regulating the movement of competitors, provide an opportunity to objectively compare some of their abilities, and ensure the maximum manifestation of physical qualities during the competition.

Keywords: Sport, athlete, competition, opponent, competition, competition, health, health, refreshment.

INTRODUCTION.

During the period of independence, Uzbek athletes have been achieving high results in international competitions and world championships, as well as in the Olympic Games. According to the achievements of our athletes on the international arena, the highest places of the shoxsupa are awarded. One of the factors that lead countries to the world is their achievements in physical culture and sports. Of course, in order to achieve these results, great responsibility and perseverance are required from our athletes. In our society, great attention is paid to the training of athletes, the construction of modern sports facilities, and the holding of many international competitions in our country. As a member of international sports associations, Uzbekistan participates in international competitions and Olympic games as an equal competitor. Our country is a member of sports associations, and the National Olympic Committee of our Republic was established in our capital city of Tashkent. With the goal of hosting the Summer Olympics in the near future, the construction of sports facilities that can fully meet the requirements of the world standard is being carried out rapidly.

MAIN PART.

Taking personal care of one's health should be inculcated from a young age through the family, school, neighborhood, health care system, physical education and sports. It is important to note that from the first years of independence, when the honorable man said that people should value their health and protect it as a national treasure, not in words, but in practice, great attention has been paid to physical education and sports in our country, and to the development of the young generation. As a result of these educations, Uzbek boys and girls are achieving positive results in international competitions and Olympic Games.

Countless events are being organized in our country to ensure the physical and spiritual well-being of our future young generation. Organization of a healthy lifestyle of schoolchildren and students of higher educational institutions creates an opportunity to contribute to the development and development of our country in cooperation with all young people. Raising the young generation to be physically fit and up-to-date places great responsibilities on physical education trainers and their students. Therefore, a number of reforms are being carried out in the organization of physical education activities in the educational system. It is an important issue to expand the range of theoretical knowledge of physical education and sports to students of vocational colleges and secondary general education schools. Providing recommendations on organizing a healthy lifestyle and doing physical exercises independently is one of the activities that are very necessary today.

Sports competitions, as a unique activity, play a major role in regulating the movement of competitors, provide an opportunity to objectively compare some of their abilities and ensure the maximum manifestation of physical qualities during the competition.

The sport in its current form has a number of distinctive features:

- 1) in the activity of sports competitions, the level of competition increases with the requirements for successive achievements, organized based on the system of sports competitions (those who participated in the lower competitions are placed in the upper ring or from the bottom to the top).
- 2) it is carried out due to the equalization of actions performed directly in competitions, management conditions and methods of evaluating achievements. This equalization is reinforced by certain rules as general norms of conducting competitions.
- 3) competitors' behavior is regulated according to the principles of competition.

The athlete displays the indicators of the chosen type, individually, according to his capabilities.

These results can be defined in units of time, distance, weight to improve the result of either physical victory or victory over the opponent (in points, goals, points, etc.).

A high sports result is a benchmark of human potential in today's development of sports. By comparing them, everyone can compare their sports results, and based on this, it is possible to plan to improve the results. From the above, it is clear that the role of benchmarking and encouraging sports results.

Sports results are always a multifactorial phenomenon (which depends on many causes). The results of sports in the society are considered to be the factors influencing the development.

- 1) Athlete's individual talent and level of preparation for high results.
- 2) Effectiveness of the sports training system, analysis of its content and material-technical provision.
- 3) It depends on the breadth of the sports movement and the general social conditions of its development.

Studying the characteristics of sports competitions has been of interest to sports experts and has not lost its importance even now.

First of all, competition is the main content of sports.

Second, sports competition is "bigger" than sports training in terms of genetics and subordination. It is known that in the development of human spirituality and culture, games were first formed among various one-on-one combat and sports elements. Later, after their forms, styles and elements begin to form, the ways of preparation begin to be defined. Currently, a scientifically based system of training athletes in many fields of sports has been established, including sports training.

Thirdly, sports competitions are a "Polygon" for determining the physical tactical-technical capabilities of the athlete, reserves and the capabilities of the sports team. Therefore, competition is created to overcome psychological resistance only during the competition, and the psychological structure of the athlete's competitive activity is determined. The competition system combines a number of official and unofficial competitions and organizes sports activity as a relatively separate form. These are divided in a certain order depending on their scale, importance, stages and conditions of the athlete's training.

Absolute firsts (individual and team), world and Olympic games take the main places in competitions. Competitions aimed at such a main goal have a certain influence on the training of an athlete. Accordingly, certain stages of training are planned, optimal preparation time for high sports results, etc. are determined. Many other competitions are held for preparation. 10-15% of the total time of sports training determines the time of the competition.

A competitive activity is an organized competition that objectively compares one's abilities and ensures and regulates one's maximum performance. It has several special features:

1. To organize activities in the competition system depending on the level of increasing competition and the demand for achievement (in preliminary and official competitions).
2. In the implementation of the means of the competition, the activity of the athlete is strengthened by certain rules and the general norms of the competition.
3. It also depends on the behavior and behavior of the contestants.

Sports competitions - in the form of excitement, currently more than 100 sports competitions are held. Each type of sport has its own methodical features, conditions for participation, rules for holding and determining winners, and other requirements for holding a competition.

The competition is part of the athlete's training system, because it is organized taking into account social tasks (propaganda, exhibitionism, etc.) without personal sports training.

A sports competition is a form of competition in the form of a game, held to determine the development of physical fitness, motor skills and the art of performing exercises or thinking and reasoning.

From young athletes to skilled athletes, competition is very important.

It is impossible to talk about sports activities without participating in competitions.

Competitions are a motivating factor for athletes, and at the same time, they teach the athlete to gradually increase the load, train the will, learn to fight sports and control the training process.

Practice shows that the more an athlete participates in competitions, the more experience he has. After all, the number of competitions in all types of sports has increased.

By its very nature, the number of main competitions, which are the end point of the main training, should not be large (3-4 times a year, except for sports games). The main competitions should be arranged from simple to complex and according to their difficulty. They should be placed in this year in such a way that the athlete has the opportunity to constantly prepare for the most important

competition, to have physical and mental rest between competitions, and to correct the shortcomings identified in one competition during the training process before the next competition.

The number of sportsmen's participation during the competition depends primarily on the nature of the sport. Competitions in sports (1-2 competition days per week) are held more often than in sports with special demands on endurance and longer recovery.

It is necessary to take into account the following in the preparation system of an athlete for participation in competitions:

- competitions for an athlete should be chosen carefully and gradually become more difficult:
- participation of athletes who are equal in terms of competition days:
- it is necessary to participate in the necessary number of competitions to achieve high-level achievements:
- moving time from there to here, etc. and the increase in strength-intensive competitions can limit training and have a negative impact on the athlete's training:
- the calendar of competitions (day, distribution, level of difficulty of competitions) should be in such a way that a great opportunity is created. It is necessary to focus on this goal in all competitions.

Thus, sports competitions are a way of demonstrating achievements, evaluating and comparing the achievements of individual athletes and teams.

Sportsmen's activity during competition is called competition activity. Competition activity consists of some combinations of actions and methods aimed at achieving the highest sports results, and is provided with an integral level of technical, physical, tactical and mental preparation. Participation in sports competitions is a form of competitive activity. Sports competition is a time-limited competition, in which the abilities of the competitors are objectively compared.

A gradual increase in the level of competition and the demand for achievements (it directly depends on the results of the athlete in high-level competitions). In order to participate in the national level competitions, it is necessary to take the appropriate place in the regional competitions (of course, the competition for victory is stronger in the national competitions than in the regional ones).

By standardizing the movement of athletes, competitions, the regulations on the conditions of their performance, and the rules of sports competitions are determined:

- the procedure for holding a competition (education) within the framework of non-antagonistic (friendly) competition (competition rules).

The process of competition (sports competition) means to change the situation in the competition in an orderly manner.

The current state of the situation ensures the success of the next, while the current state of the situation depends on the previous one.

The aspect determining the athlete's competitive activity consists of the following components:

- perception of the situation;
- walking posture of opponents and partners;
- dynamics of one's situation;
- analysis of received information and comparing it with the experience and purpose of competitions; - accepting the main decision;

- implementation of the decision made in mind;

For example, in the competition activity of a wrestler, it is emphasized as follows:

- thoroughness of the fight (by the total number of methods used);
- effectiveness of attack actions;
- effectiveness of protective actions: - effectiveness of actions in tired conditions, etc.

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